

dAlry – Advanced, trustworthy AI and data solutions for individualised automated milking & feeding of dairy cows

The EU-funded dAlry 4.0 project addresses the challenge within the agricultural sector to have increased production with fewer raw materials for an improved impact on society, animals, climate, and biodiversity. The project addresses current challenges by combining AI, Data and Robotics solutions to upgrade the Automated Milking Systems (AMS) capabilities with measurable results to be demonstrated through real-world use cases. The dAlry 4.0 Consortium recently met in Netherlands, where renowned scientists from both Industry and Academia coming from 6 EU Member States, had the opportunity to join hands towards the initiation of the project.

Since the late 20th century when AMS were firstly introduced, the labour intensity for farmers has greatly improved because of the reduced manual labour and cost. Not only have these machines improved in harvesting milk efficiently, but they also have the added ability to collect a greater amount of data regarding production, milk composition, cows' health, and behaviour. Such invaluable data, allows producers to make data-based management decisions, and in parallel these data could contribute to reducing emissions and increasing animal welfare.

Nevertheless, currently available AMS still have possible development opportunities which are addressed in dAlry 4.0 to further optimise their operation. Through the project the AMS capabilities will be extended with the development of hardware and software modules. All to be integrated together for an upgraded system. The existing data management platform will be additionally extended with newly integrated tools for innovative simulations, data analysis and graphical representation. The approach will be demonstrated through real-world use cases of interest both for the farming sector and the food industry. For the initial testing period, the new modules will be tested within R&D facilities to ensure successful integration of all components and required data analysis is achieved. In addition, validations through real-world scenarios will take place on several collaborating farms. These farms are selected from various locations around Europe and are already collaborating for R&D activities relevant to AMS robots. They will be included to demonstrate the overall solution with different cow breeds, different farm sizes, feed ratios and other differing factors.

The project is a collaborative effort developed by a multi-disciplinary team and it is coordinated by CyRIC, Cyprus Research and Innovation Center Ltd, under the framework of EU's Horizon Europe Programme. The project was launched on the 1st of October 2023, and it will run for three and a half years.

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Project partners: CyRIC - Cyprus Research and Innovation Centre (Cyprus), Lely Industries (Netherlands), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Spain), Aristoteleio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (Greece), Technische Universität Wien (Austria), Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutou Systimatou Epikoinonion kai Ypologiston (Greece) and Alpes Lasers SA (Switzerland).

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Notes for editors:

1. Horizon Europe is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €95.5 billion of funding available over 7 years (2021 to 2027) – in addition to the private investment that this money will attract. It promises more breakthroughs, discoveries, and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market.

2. For media enquiries, please contact CyRIC on +357 22 777200 or e-mail info@cyric.eu

3. Project online presence:

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Logos:

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